

These are five definitions:

1. The definition of true is: It happens, however will it happen again? It's happening, however will it exist as happening again? It's happened, and what has happened doesn't happen again.
2. The definition of false is: Does it happen? Is it happening? Has it happened?
3. The definition of falser is: Does it happen?? Is it happening?? Has it happened??
4. The definition of falsest is: Does it happen??? Is it happening??? Has it happened???
5. The definition of truest is: It happens, and it stays that way. It's happening, and it stays that way. It's happened, and it stays that way.

This set is timed as 9:13, and is dated as the 10th day of the 2nd month, of the 2025th year.